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Editors Message...

In globalised era Higher Education Plays very crucial role in Development of Nation, as it empowers the individuals with necessary competence for achieving important personal, social and higher level of professional goals. Its importance depicted by words of first Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru “A university stands for humanism, for tolerance, for reason, for the adventure of the ideas and for the search of truth. It stands for onward march of human race towards even higher objectives. If the universities discharge their duties adequately, then it well with the nation and the people”. India's higher education system is the world's third largest in terms of students, next to China and the United States. Policies and approach adopted by Indian government after implementation of economic reforms are not favorable to the higher education. Since the reforms period there has been a continuously decline in the budgetary allocations made by the government to fund higher education in India. Present paper aims to find out new trends in higher education in India. Paper also discusses various challenges in the field higher education in India.

India has the largest higher educational system with respect to the number of institutions. After the independence of the country, the state and central governments have given great attention to the development of higher education. As a result, the system of higher education in India has seen an impressive growth in terms of a number of universities and colleges. The share of the unaided private sector has increased significantly since 2001 in terms of the number of institutions and enrollment. Indian higher education System comprises three stages – under graduate level, post graduate level and doctorate level. The Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) is highest body of Governance which is responsible for supervising the higher education system through UGC. Higher education in India has expanded rapidly over the past two decades. This growth has been mainly driven by private sector initiatives. India's Higher Education sector has witnessed a tremendous increase in the number of Universities/ University level Institutions & Colleges since independence Indian higher education presently includes 892 universities out of which 48 central universalities, 394 state universities, 125 deemed universities and 325 private universities. Apart from the above universities, other institutions are granted the permission to autonomously award degrees. However, they do not affiliate colleges and are not officially called ‘universities’ but ‘autonomous organizations’ or “autonomous institutes”. They fall under the administrative control of the Department of Higher Education. These organizations include Indian institute of Technology, Indian Institutes of Management, National Institute of Technology and All India Institute of Medical Sciences.

Dr. Bapug Gholap

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concerned to the rural development. Rural sector, therefore, is prepared to emerge as a major contributor in economic development of our country. It has been rightly said, "In the end, however, rural development should not be seen as a package of specific needs but as a transformation of rural like and conditions.

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08

A STUDY OF FAMILY CLIMATE OF RURAL AND URBAN B.Ed. TEACHER-TRAINEES OF BAREILLY DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to find out the difference of family climate of B.Ed. teacher-trainees in relation to their locality. Descriptive survey method was used for this study. Sample consisting 120 B.Ed. teacher-trainees was selected by using random sampling technique from 4 B.Ed. colleges of Bareilly district. Family Climate Scale developed by Harpreet Bhatia & N.K. Chadha (2019) used for data collection. Data was analyzed using Mean, S.D. and t-test. Finding reveals that no significant difference has been found in cohesion, expressiveness, conflict and recreational dimensions of family climate of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees. Significant difference has been found in different dimensions of family climate of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Keywords: Family Climate, B.Ed. Teacher-Trainees, Locality

Introduction:

The overall achievement of a child

depends on or is affected by personal as well as social factors. Several researches in the field of education have led us to the belief that family climate of one individual is the most important determinant of academic achievement. The family is supposed to play a vital role in the progress of independence, individuality, and accomplishment of the child. The family climate may differ in several aspects viz, socioeconomic status, educational environment, type of family, etc. Each family environment is unique in itself and it consists of different types of individuals in a different surroundings. Family Climate exerts a deep and persistent influence on the life of the individual, for it is the family in which he acquires the intimate experiences. Family climate moulds the behaviour, personality, attitude, aptitude, self-esteem and mental health of an individual (Kaur et al, 2015)

Family climate plays an important role in every field of student's life. In this specific context the present research will undertaken to specifically provide empirical answers of these questions like what is difference of different dimensions of family climate of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees. Family Climate Scale developed by Harpreet Bhatia & N.K. Chadha (2019) used for this research. This scale of 69 items contains three main dimensions.

(!) Relationship Dimensions: Cohesion, Expressiveness, Conflict, Acceptance & caring

(a!) Personal Growth Dimensions: Independence & Active recreational Orientation

(b!) System Maintenance Dimensions: Organisation & Control

Formal definition of locality is "A small area of country or city is called locality." These are two types of locality urban and rural. Urban area have many facilities like transport, electricity, safe & clean drinking water, many school, college and university, coaching facilities etc. Rural area has not proper facilities of citizen/people. So rural area less developed than urban area.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To explore family climate of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
2. To study family climate of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees on different dimensions of family climate.
3. To investigate family climate of rural male and rural female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
4. To study family climate of rural male and rural female B.Ed. teacher-trainees on different dimensions of family climate.
5. To explore the family climate of urban male and urban female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
6. To detect family climate of urban male and urban female B.Ed. teacher-trainees on different dimensions of family climate.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. There is no significant difference in family climate of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
2. There is no significant difference in family climate of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees on different dimensions of family climate.
3. There is no significant difference in family climate of rural male and rural female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
4. There is no significant difference in family climate of rural male and rural female B.Ed. teacher-trainees on different dimensions of family climate.
5. There is no significant difference in family climate of urban male and urban female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.
6. There is no significant difference in family climate of urban male and urban female B.Ed. teacher-trainees on different dimensions of family climate.

Research Design & Methodology:

The researcher used Descriptive Survey method for conducting this research. Population of the present study consists of all the teacher-trainees of B.Ed. colleges affiliated to M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly. Sample of 120 teacher-trainees of four B.Ed. colleges of Bareilly district were selected with the help of

simple random sampling techniques. **Family Climate Scale (FCS)** developed by Harpreet Bhatia & N.K.Chadha(2019) was used for the study. Data were analysed using Mean, S.D., and t-test.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in family climate of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table-1: Family climate of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees

Groups of Locality	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	df	Result
Rural	60	245.15	17.365	3.193**	118	Significant at 0.01 Level
Urban	60	256.68	21.935			

From Table-1, the t-value is 3.193 which is significant at both 0.05 and 0.01 level. So our null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in family climate of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher trainees is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. Thus there exists significant difference in family climate of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees. The mean score of urban B.Ed. teacher trainees is 256.68, which is higher than that of rural B.Ed. teacher trainees (245.15). So it can be concluded that Urban B.Ed. teacher trainees have better family climate.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in family climate of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees on different dimensions of family climate.

Table-2: Family climate of rural and urban B.Ed. teacher-trainees on different dimensions of family climate

Dimension of Family Climate	Groups of Locality	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	df	Result
Cohesion	Rural	60	51.90	5.442	3.120**	118	Significant at 0.01 level
	Urban	60	48.22	7.349			
Expressiveness	Rural	60	30.58	3.738	3.977**	118	Significant at 0.01 level
	Urban	60	34.23	6.046			
Conflict	Rural	60	40.18	4.876	4.357**	118	Significant at 0.01 level
	Urban	60	44.98	7.002			
Acceptance and caring	Rural	60	44.12	5.089	2.288**	118	Significant at 0.01 level
	Urban	60	41.25	8.266			
Independence	Rural	60	29.15	4.120	5.829**	118	Significant at 0.01 level
	Urban	60	34.37	5.575			
Active Recreational	Rural	60	27.65	3.521	5.391**	118	Significant at 0.01 level
	Urban	60	31.75	4.389			
Organization	Rural	60	7.55	1.578	1.054	118	Insignificant
	Urban	60	7.20	2.032			
Control	Rural	60	14.02	2.480	1.773	118	Insignificant
	Urban	60	14.87	2.765			

The above Table-2 shows that the t-value of Cohesion, Expressiveness, Conflict, Acceptance & caring, Independence and Active Recreation are 3.12, 3.977, 4.357, 2.288, 5.829, 5.391 respectively which are significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance whereas t-value of Organisation and Control are 1.054 and 1.773 respectively which are not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence null hypothesis on Cohesion, Expressiveness, Conflict, Acceptance & caring, Independence and Active Recreation dimensions is rejected and it is accepted on two dimensions i.e. organization and control.

From above table -2, it is also revealed that mean score of urban B.Ed. teacher trainees is higher in all the dimensions as compared to their counterparts. So, it can be concluded that family climate of Urban B.Ed. teacher trainees is better.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in family climate of rural male and rural female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table-3: Family climate of Rural male and Rural female B.Ed. teacher-trainees

Groups of Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	df	Result
Rural Male	26	242.62	11.819	1.059	58	Not significant
Rural Female	34	245.09	20.601			

From Table-3, it is found that the t-value is 1.059 at df 58 which is not significant at 0.05 level. So null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in family climate of rural male and rural female B.Ed. teacher trainees is accepted. Thus there exist no significant difference in family climate of rural male and rural female B.Ed. teacher-trainees. However, Mean score of rural Male B.Ed. teacher trainees is 242.39 and mean score of urban female B.Ed. teacher trainees is 245.09 which clearly reveals that family climate is better for rural males.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in family climate of rural male and rural female B.Ed. teacher-trainees on different dimensions of family climate.

Table-4: Family climate of rural male and rural female B.Ed. teacher-trainees on different dimensions of family climate

Dimension of Family Climate	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	df	Result
Cohesion	Male	26	52.50	5.046	0.757	58	Not significant
	Female	34	51.44	5.759			
Expressiveness	Male	26	30.15	3.574	0.784	58	Not significant
	Female	34	30.91	3.880			
Conflict	Male	26	38.62	3.699	2.363*	58	Significant at 0.05 level
	Female	34	41.38	5.360			
Acceptance and caring	Male	26	46.08	4.471	2.398*	58	Significant at 0.05 level
	Female	34	42.62	5.081			
Independence	Male	26	27.69	3.473	2.581**	58	Significant at 0.05 level
	Female	34	30.26	4.273			
Active Recreational	Male	26	26.23	2.471	3.063**	58	Significant at 0.05 level
	Female	34	28.74	3.840			
Organization	Male	26	7.42	1.391	0.557	58	Not significant
	Female	34	7.65	1.721			
Control	Male	26	13.92	2.622	0.251	58	Not significant
	Female	34	14.09	2.404			

The above Table-4 shows that the t-value of, Conflict, Acceptance & caring, Independence and Active Recreation are 2.363, 2.398, 2.581, 3.063 respectively which are significant at 0.05 level of significance whereas t-value of Cohesion, Expressiveness, Organisation and Control are 0.757, 0.784, 0.557 and 0.251 respectively which are not significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence null hypothesis on Conflict, Acceptance & caring, Independence and Active Recreation dimensions is rejected and it is accepted on dimensions i.e. Cohesion, Expressiveness, organization and control. From above table -2, it is also revealed that mean score of rural female B.Ed. teacher trainees is higher in all the dimensions as compared to their counterparts. So, it can be concluded that family climate of Rural females B.Ed. teacher trainees is better.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant difference in family climate of urban male and urban female B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Table-5: Family climate of urban male and urban female B.Ed. teacher-trainees

Groups of Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Df	Result
Urban Male	18	259.39	9.971	0.845	58	Not significant
Urban Female	42	255.52	25.427			

From Table-5, it is found that the t-value

is 0.845 at df 58 which is not significant at 0.05 level. So null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in family climate of urban male and urban female B.Ed. teacher trainees is accepted. Thus there exist no significant difference in family climate of urban male and urban female B.Ed. teacher-trainees. However, Mean score of Urban Male B.Ed. teacher trainees is 259.39 and mean score of urban female B.Ed. teacher trainees is 255.52 which clearly reveals that family climate is better for urban males.

Hypothesis 6: There is no significant difference in family climate of urban male and urban female B.Ed. teacher-trainees on different dimensions of family climate.

Table-6: Family climate of urban male urban female B.Ed. teacher-trainees on different dimensions of family climate

Dimension of Family Climate	Groups of Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-value	df	Result
Cohesion	Male	18	42.11	2.494	6.944**	58	Significant at 0.01 level
	Female	42	50.83	7.194			
Expressiveness	Male	18	40.39	3.127	8.260**	58	Significant at 0.01 level
	Female	42	31.60	4.978			
Conflict	Male	18	50.89	4.391	5.907**	58	Significant at 0.01 level
	Female	42	42.45	6.379			
Acceptance and caring	Male	18	31.39	2.570	12.910**	58	Significant at 0.01 level
	Female	42	45.48	5.882			
Independence	Male	18	39.50	2.333	7.645**	58	Significant at 0.01 level
	Female	42	32.17	5.094			
Active Recreational	Male	18	36.22	2.130	9.020**	58	Significant at 0.01 level
	Female	42	29.57	3.500			
Organization	Male	18	5.22	1.517	6.514**	58	Significant at 0.01 level
	Female	42	8.05	1.592			
Control	Male	18	13.67	2.169	2.540*	58	Significant at 0.05 level
	Female	42	15.38	2.854			

The above Table-4 shows that the t-value of Cohesion, Expressiveness, Conflict, Acceptance & caring, Independence, Active Recreation, Organisation and Control are 6.944, 8.260, 5.907, 12.91, 7.645, 9.02, 6.514 and 2.540 respectively at df 58 which are highly significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. Hence null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in family climate of urban male and urban female B.Ed. teacher-trainees on different dimensions of family climate is rejected.

Conclusion:

As we have found from our findings that

there exists significant difference in family climate of Rural and Urban B.Ed. teacher trainees. Family climate of Urban B.Ed. teacher trainees is far better than that of rural B.Ed. teacher trainees. The reason of this finding may be related to educational level of parents. Educated parents tries to understand the problem of their children and provide friendly and democratic environment to their wards. It is also found that male students have better family climate in all dimensions because more attention is given to male as compare to female. In the present study female students are more prone to unfavourable family climate in comparison to male students. Thus, it is evident that boys receive more attention and guidance at home in comparison to girls.

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09

Women Empowerment: Issues and Challenges

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Abstract:

Women Empowerment is known as the empowerment of women in our present society. Women Empowerment is an old concept. It is quite well known concept in the world. Empowerment is very essential in the society. Empowerment means individuals acquiring the power to think and act freely and fulfill their potentials as full and equal number of society.

Empowerment is synonym for power and responsibility. Women despite their value in family, society and state, are not treated at par with men. Women Empowerment envisages overall and meaningful capability building of women. Oxford Dictionary defined 'Empowerment as to make stronger and more confident, especially in controlling their life and claiming their rights.'

Nelson Mandela once said "Education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the world." "All gets lost without knowledge we become animals without wisdom."- Savitribai Phule. "I measure the progress of a community by the degree of progress which women have achieved."- Dr. B.R. Ambedkar

Keyword: Women Empowerment, development, education

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